

The Role of Research Obsession in Shifting ChatGPT into a Plagiarism Tool

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the dynamic landscape of artificial intelligence, with a particular focus on the consequences of the extensive utilization of ChatGPT's which participates in transformation it from a conversational language model to a potential tool that facilitates plagiarism for research purposes because of research obsession. As the digital age advances and with the increasing prevalence of academic dishonesty and content theft, there is a growing need for sophisticated tools to identify and fight plagiarism. As a result, the concerns about the ethical use of artificial intelligence are becoming increasingly important. This article examines the impact of research obsession on the development of ChatGPT and the unintended consequences that led to its misuse as a plagiarism tool. This study aims too to explore the underlying factors that have a part in this change, the ethical implications, and the possible remedies that can be used to help in to responsible AI development. The study hopes to contribute to the advancement of the discussion about plagiarism that depends on ChatGPT and enhance discussions on the responsible and ethical use of such technologies. By debating the effect of the research obsession on shifting ChatGPT to a tool for plagiarism, the study hopes to open new avenues for enhancing the integrity of academic and creative works in the digital era.

INTRODUCTION

The development of communication skills which are similar to those of a human being has been a major turning point in the continuously changing field of artificial intelligence. One such accomplishment is ChatGPT, a powerful language model that has been created in order to comprehend and produce meaningful texts in response to input instructions. In this investigation, ChatGPT's journey-which was initially meant to be a tool for facilitating natural language communication-takes an unexpected turn, running into the field of research obsession and its transforming influences on the model's original function. As scientists work passionately to improve ChatGPT's efficiency, it becomes more difficult to distinguish between innovation and unexpected effects. This study aims to examine an odd aspect of ChatGPT's development that is its unintended shifting into a tool that may be used for plagiarism. This unanticipated shift is mostly the result of the model's excessive information appetite, or what can be named "research obsession." An obsessive need for searching through large databases, scholarly archives, and internet sources to find material outside of the scope of their initial design is a symptom of this research addiction. This addiction has serious consequences, because ChatGPT unintentionally breaks ethical boundaries and becomes a possible tool for plagiarism. Because of the model's remarkable ability to reproduce text in a coherent manner, questions have been raised regarding the potential ethical consequences of its unintended uses. In order to understand the complex dynamics behind ChatGPT's research obsession, the study set out on a curious endeavor. It aims to examine the processes that give rise to this phenomenon and investigate the situations whereby the model's search for information gives rise to unexpected features. By shedding light on the relationship between research obsession and the emergence of ChatGPT as a plagiarism tool, the study hopes to start critical discussions about the ethical dimensions of artificial intelligence development and the responsible deployment of such advanced language models in the field of information synthesis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The world has gone through dramatic and dynamic transformation thanks in technology to generative artificial intelligence, which enables people to produce original content, text, photos, audio, fiction facts, and video material but not citation, humor or irony (Mondal, et al, 2023:1; Pokotylo, 2023:87; Abd Rahim, et al, 2023:70). ChatGPT which stands for Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer and has intensive training in a variety of textual sources, including books, articles, and websites possesses a comprehensive understanding of natural language is a conversational artificial intelligence chatbot that is developed by OpenAI where is used as an educational aid to reply to students' questions, give feedback, help virtual conversations, improve the ways in which foreign languages are taught and evaluated, and to be a writing helper to aid people create grammatically accurate and logical texts, although it is important to be aware that the utilization of artificial intelligence poses notable obstacles and ethical dilemmas which requires careful consideration must be given to

issues like data privacy, equitable access to education, and the effect on the role of the educator (Dempere, et al, 2023:2; Ganapathy, 2023:132; Hang, 2023:6; Ghafar, 2023:73; Montenegro-Rueda, 2023:1). In the same way that people use gadgets such as calculators, computers, and even paper and pen, they can incorporate artificial intelligence into education and teach students how to employ it wisely and to educate them about the moral consequences of using artificial intelligence in society, formal and informal education, as well as continuous learning (Bozkurt, et al, 2023:60). Two performance-related debates are connected to ChatGPT: one involves information accuracy, while the other raises ethical questions about utilizing ChatGPT for plagiarism in academic and research contexts (Szabo, 2023:25-26; Cotton, et al., 2023:2; Jarrah, et al, 2023:3). The prevalence of academic plagiarism has increased in educational environments due to its discovery in a wide range of student projects, reports, assignments, and other types of work as academic plagiarism is characterized as the use of concepts, ideas, or structures without giving proper credit to the original author (Elkhatat, et al, 2023:1).

Research Objectives

The study will attempt to answer the following three objectives.

Examine the reasons that caused ChatGPT to become a tool for plagiarism.

Analyze the moral consequences of making ChatGPT as a tool for plagiarism.

Propose solutions to address the concerns of shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism.

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to examine the transformation of ChatGPT into a plagiarism detection tool. It uses a multiple method to achieve this goal, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze the data and provide relevant outcomes and solutions. Investigating a wide-ranging dataset including academic journals, internet articles, and other written materials provides the basis of the present research. These methods, along with an in-depth review of the data, allowed for a full investigation of the role that research obsession had in turning ChatGPT into a plagiarism tool. The outcomes hope to point out how research obsession-driven demands for scientific articles might turn ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism.

Research Obsession

Within the dynamic field of knowledge acquisition, people's desire for understanding and knowledge frequently leads them into the fascinating world of research. While it is admirable that people are interested in learning new things, there is a fine line distinguishing truthful curiosity from a passionate obsession for research. Different topics and fields are affected by research obsession, which can take various shapes. Motivation may be significantly improved by the attraction of solving global challenges, broadening the boundaries of knowledge, and contributing to humankind's collective knowledge. Like any strong enthusiasm, it has a number of difficulties, however. An overwhelming feeling of competition might result from a research

obsession. Researchers may feel pressured to save money, break ethical principles, or place quantity before quality in the rush for fame and the publishing of new findings. The trust that society has in the results of studies can be harmed by this, as it might undermine the validity of the methodology used in science. While carrying out studies in order to acquire knowledge is a noble activity, human beings must be aware of the risks associated with research obsession. In this study, the term "research obsession" is meant to refer to the overuse of ChatGPT for content creation without an adequate comprehension or awareness of the heavy reliance on this artificial intelligence technology. The phenomenon creates ethical questions, especially if it results in the model being wrongly used as a tool for plagiarism.

DISCUSSION

The shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism raises important issues about the role of research obsession in doing this. This section aims to probe the role research obsession in changing the artificial intelligence tool of ChatGPT to a tool of plagiarism. Plagiarism represents a serious violation of the ethics of writing and creativity, where ideas, phrases, or literary works are copied or stolen without permission from their original owner. This act is unethical and contradicts the values of integrity and individual success in the world of knowledge. Plagiarism is a violation of the intellectual property rights of writers and artists. Authors strive to create their literary works through their unique thinking and personal experiences, and when these ideas are used without permission they lose part of their literary identity. Plagiarism negatively affects innovation and creativity in society. If authors feel that their work might be easily stolen, they may be reluctant to share their ideas or write more boldly, resulting in a loss of the diversity and richness of the literature. To combat the phenomenon of plagiarism, awareness must be enhanced of the importance of intellectual property rights and the necessity of respecting literary works to contribute to building a literary community based on integrity and mutual respect. Plagiarism creates negative consequences and impacts on multiple levels, whether ethically, scientifically or economically. In terms of ethical consequences, it leads to a loss of integrity and trust, as committing plagiarism leads to a loss of integrity and trust between writers and creators, which makes the scientific community lose the ability to rely on each other ethically. Plagiarism also leads to discrediting the person involved in this act, as it can lead to the discrediting of the person involved in this act, which affects the public's understanding of his personality and creative abilities and looks at him in a negative light, doubting his abilities. Plagiarism also leads to scientific consequences, such as undermining research and innovation, as it undermines the research and creative spirit in society, as writers, artists, and authors may stop exchanging ideas and experiences for fear of illegal imitation. Plagiarism also leads to a low level of quality, as relying on plagiarism can lead to a low level of quality in literary and artistic works as ideas are imitated rather than developed. Plagiarism also leads to economic consequences by harming the creative and cultural industries because plagiarism negatively affects the

creative and cultural production and industries as the motivation for writers and creators to produce more artistic and literary works may decrease. Plagiarism also leads to the loss of economic opportunities, as the spread of plagiarism leads to the loss of economic opportunities for writers, artists, and authors, so that it becomes difficult for them to market their works and benefit from them economically. There is no doubt that plagiarism not only affects the individuals who are directly affected by it, but also causes obvious harm to the society as a whole, threatening innovation, cultural and economic progress. Plagiarism can have social consequences, such as undermining the values of society. Plagiarism affects the values of society, as people lose respect and appreciation for creativity and literary works, which reflects negatively on the culture and intellectual spirit of society. Plagiarism can weaken the spirit of solidarity, as plagiarism can lead to the disintegration of society and the weakening of the spirit of solidarity, making people less willing to support each other in the fields of creativity and culture. Plagiarism can lead to legal consequences, which requires emphasis on intellectual property rights because the repeated cases of plagiarism can lead to increased emphasis on intellectual property rights and the development of more effective laws to protect the rights of writers and authors which urges for legal penalties for individuals who commit plagiarism the matter that would encourage respect for the intellectual property rights and limits and reduces the occurrence of this type of violation. Plagiarism can cause psychological consequences such as loss of inspiration and the desire to create because the painful discovery of the theft of ideas may lead to a loss of inspiration and desire to create among the affected individuals which can affect the level of their creative production. Plagiarism can also increase psychological tension and anxiety among authors and creators, as they fear that their works will be illegally infringed. Confronting plagiarism requires integrated efforts from all sectors of the society including education, religion, laws, and encouraging innovation and cooperation to preserve moral values and promote cultural and economic development.

Objective One: Examine the reasons that caused ChatGPT to become a tool for plagiarism.

This part will investigate the first objective of the study by examining the reasons that stand behind shifting ChatGPT to become a tool for plagiarism. The evolution of ChatGPT from a communicative artificial intelligence to an unintended tool for plagiarism can be traced back to several factors that emerged as users explored its great capabilities. While initially it was designed for natural language interaction, the unintended consequences of the model's adaptability and users' behavior led to its unexpected role into a tool that facilitates plagiarism. The following factors can be said to be claimed reasons for shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism. The generative nature of ChatGPT as its primary function is to generate human-like text based on the inputs it receives. This generative nature, while promoting creativity and different conversational output, but it opened wide avenues for users who want to exploit the model for having content generation without tiring. This unintended use made the groundwork for ChatGPT to be shifted into a tool for

plagiarism. Unlike other conventional writing tools that have built-in attribution features, ChatGPT lacks an inherent mechanism that can be used to have credit sources or to provide proper citations. Users, either intentionally or inadvertently, started getting benefit of the model to produce contents without explicitly acknowledging the original authors or sources, the matter that leads to the unintentional shifting of ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism. Users found that ChatGPT can be used for more than just informal discussions. So many of them start testing the model's capabilities by using it to generate different writings such as essays, articles, or academic content, often with neglecting or ignoring the importance of proper citations. This experimental application unintentionally opened the way for the tool to be used as an immediate solution for content generation, further destroying moral barriers. Another factor that may have caused ChatGPT to become a tool for plagiarism is the ambiguity regarding ethical rules. This is because the use of artificial intelligence tools ethically is frequently a matter of personal interpretation. The company that created ChatGPT, OpenAI, first offered recommendations for appropriate usage but had trouble establishing and upholding moral limits. Because of this uncertainty, there existed a gloomy area where some users took use of the model for goals that were against to ethical standards for material production. Although ChatGPT was not intended to be a teaching tool, its usage in academic contexts for a variety of reasons unintentionally led to misuse. Some students used ChatGPT as a solution because they were under pressure to complete original work; however, they ignored the value of independent thought and appropriate references. This misuse played an important role in the tool's unintentional connection with plagiarism. It can be said that ChatGPT's unintentional transformation into tool for plagiarism can serve as an indicator of the subtle relationship that exists between users' behavior, the generative capabilities of the model, and the increasing ethical issues. To reduce the unintentional connection between ChatGPT and plagiarism, it would be very important to address these unintended consequences and encourage responsible artificial intelligence use while the tool is updated and improved.

Objective Two: Analyze the moral consequences of making ChatGPT as a tool for plagiarism.

This part will investigate the second objective of the study which aims to analyze the moral consequences of making ChatGPT as a tool for plagiarism. The inadvertent conversion of ChatGPT into a plagiarism tool presents important ethical issues that go beyond technology. A number of ethical issues occur when users take use of the model's generating capabilities for personal and professional benefit without giving proper credit, emphasizing the necessity of considering the ethical consequences of such unintentional uses. The following are some moral concerns that may be attributed to turning ChatGPT into a plagiarism-inducing tool. When ChatGPT is used as a plagiarism tool, it can compromise and violate the core and basic values of academic transparency and honesty. Presenting someone else's work as one's own is plagiarism, which violates and undermines the basic principles of integrity, scholarship, and intellectual responsibility. This moral outcome is

especially concerning because it calls to question the basic foundations of educational frameworks that are based on the acquisition of information and creativity. By depending on ChatGPT to generate content without proper attribution, users go through the risk of devaluing the importance of original thoughts and creativity. The moral fabric of intellectual pursuits is woven with the appreciation of unique perspectives and insights. The use of the tool for plagiarism diminishes the significance of individual contributions and compromises the ethos of fostering genuine innovation. Paying attention to the different viewpoints, opinions and ideas is embedded into the moral structure of intellectual activities, so the value of individual contributions is diminished and the culture of encouraging genuine creativity is harmed when the tool is used for plagiarism. The public's confidence in artificial intelligence is damaged when ChatGPT is abused for plagiarism. As artificially intelligent systems grow more and more incorporated into our daily lives, it is important to maintain accountability, ethics, and transparency. The use of such tools for immoral reasons might limit the adoption of constructive applications by creating a larger dissatisfaction towards the responsible employment of artificial intelligence. The use of ChatGPT for plagiarism raises concerns about ethical conduct in professional settings because the misrepresentation of generated content as original work cannot only harm the integrity of professional outputs but also challenges the ethical standards that are expected to be used in various industries. In fact, the moral consequences of shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism can go beyond the issues of professional responsibility, honesty, and accountability. The unintended transformation of ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism highlights the responsibility of artificial intelligence industries to continually assess and address the ethical implications and consequences of its products. Maintaining a good balance between technological innovations and ethical considerations is important for maintaining public trust and ensuring the responsible use of artificial intelligence tools. The ethical consequences of shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism go beyond the immediate act of content misuse as they exceed the foundations of education, creativity, trust in technology, and professional ethics. It is crucial to manage these morally complicated issues as society struggles with the rapidly changing artificial intelligent environment in order to prevent the unintended consequences of technology from undermining the ethical foundation that supports the professional and academic efforts.

Objective Three: Propose solutions to address the concerns of shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism.

This part will suggest solutions to address the concerns of shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism. Addressing the concerns of ChatGPT being used as a tool for plagiarism requires a multifaceted approach involving technological, educational, and ethical considerations. The following is an attempt to propose some suggested solutions. Artificial intelligence companies should take in consideration the establishing and communicating clear and comprehensive ethical guidelines for the use of ChatGPT. These guidelines should explicitly discourage any form of plagiarism or unethical use

of the tool. Artificial intelligence companies can collaborate with educators, researchers, and artificial intelligence ethicists to develop guidelines that balance innovation with responsible use. Implementing a built-in citation mechanism within ChatGPT can be of good help to encourage users to acknowledge and pay respect to the sources of data and information. This could be an automatic feature that generates proper citations based on the input data. By promoting proper attribution, the tool can actively discourage plagiarism and reinforce the importance of academic integrity. Artificial intelligence companies should have educational campaigns that aim to raise public awareness about the ethical uses of ChatGPT. Targeting people in general and educators and students in particular, these campaigns can provide guidelines on responsible artificial intelligence use, highlight the consequences of shifting ChatGPT to a tool for plagiarism, and emphasize the value of original thoughts and creative thinking in academic and professional settings. The artificial intelligence companies can cooperate with educational institutions to integrate ChatGPT responsibly into the learning environment. This collaboration can involve developing educational modules on artificial intelligence morals and ethics, plagiarism, and responsible content creation. Institutions can then incorporate these modules into their curricula to ensure that students understand the ethical implications of artificial intelligence use. Establishing users' feedback and reporting mechanism can empower the community to identify and report instances of unethical use. Artificial intelligence companies can use this feedback to continually refine and improve the models, addressing emerging concerns and ensuring that the tools evolve responsibly based on users' experiences. Artificial Intelligence should have to regular model updates that focus on improving the ethical and moral and considerations and to address any unintended consequences. By staying proactive in refining the model, these companies can be ready to adapt to any emerging challenges and continuously enhance the tool's ability to discourage and decrease plagiarism and promote responsible and authentic usage. Promote responsible artificial intelligence development practices across the industry by sharing lessons learned from ChatGPT's evolution. Artificial intelligence industries can actively engage with other artificial intelligence developers, researchers, and organizations to enhance a collective commitment to ethical artificial intelligence deployment and discourage the misuse of similar technologies. Cooperation with legal experts to explore the possibility of finding the best legal safeguards within the use of artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT. This might involve clearly outlining the responsibilities of both users and providers and emphasizing on the importance of adhering to copyrights and intellectual property laws. Providing comprehensive training materials and tutorials for users to understand the capabilities and limitations of ChatGPT can help in preventing shifting it into a tool for plagiarism. This educational content can include explicit guidance on ethical uses, proper citation practices, and the potential consequences of plagiarism which will help in enhancing a culture of responsible use artificial intelligence tools. By implementing such solutions, it can be claimed that the artificial intelligence industries can reduce the possible

concerns associated with ChatGPT being used as a tool for plagiarism, promoting a responsible and ethical integration of advanced artificial intelligence technologies into academic and professional environments.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the exploration of the role of research obsession in transforming ChatGPT into a plagiarism tool has shed light on the potential implications and ethical considerations surrounding the use of advanced language models. The issue of research obsession which plays a role in shifting ChatGPT into a tool for plagiarism raises important questions about the balance between innovation and responsible usage. While the integration of research capabilities into ChatGPT enhances its ability to generate coherent and contextually relevant responses, the transformation into a plagiarism tool introduces ethical concerns related to privacy, consent, and the unintended consequences of artificial intelligence applications. It is important to know the positive aspects of using artificial intelligence tools for preventing using ChatGPT as a tool for plagiarism by enhancing academic integrity and maintaining the credibility of scholarly work. However, having a balance between empowering and supporting users with valuable research capabilities and safeguarding against misuse is very important issue. The responsible development and deployment of artificial intelligence technologies require having strong ethical frameworks, transparent guidelines, and continuous oversight in order to ensure and guarantee that these tools will cope with social and scientific values and norms. As humanity navigates the dynamic and rapid landscape of artificial intelligence applications, it becomes important to engage in open and inclusive discussions which can include researchers, developers, policymakers, and end-users to raise the awareness about the dangers of shifting ChatGPT into a tool of plagiarism. Cooperative efforts are important to establish ethical standards, promote responsible artificial intelligence practices, and reduce the potential risks that are associated with transforming sophisticated language models into tools with significant academic impacts. In order to continue the pursuit of innovation, it is very important for the artificial intelligence community to support ethical and moral values and principles, give priority for the user well-being, and contribute to the development of technologies that positively contribute to the advancement of knowledge while minimizing negative consequences.

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